

REVIEW ARTICLE ON RASAYANA (REJUVENATION THERAPY)

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INTRODUCTION

The description of Rasayana comes in detail in all the Ayurvedic texts. This branch of Ayurveda appears to have been practiced in ancient times as an important specialty aiming at rejuvenation and geriatric care. Rasayana is one of the eight branches of Ayurveda. Rasayana Chikitsa has importance from both the preventive and curative aspects of the disease. So much importance is given to this particular branch that the chapters of Rasayana find foremost place in the Charaka Samhita Chikitsa sthana. Whereas Charaka Samhita describes Rasayana in the first padas of Chikitsa Sthana in Sushruta Samhita, it is pushed back to chapters 27-30 of Chikitsa sthana. In Astang Hridaya Rasayana does not find a special place in Chikitsa sthana and is described only briefly in the 39th chapter of Uttar Tantra. This reflects on the declining importance of Rasayana therapy in the Samhita period itself.

To procure Purusartha Catustaya, i.e., Dharma, Artha, Kama, and Moksa, leading a healthy and long lifespan is very much essential. A healthy life can lead to the attainment of Ubhaya-loka Hita (Ihaloka and Paraloka), which is subdivided into Pranaisana, Dhanaisana, and Paralokaisana, three basic desires or pursuits of life. Pranaisana is prima vitae because the other two can be achieved if and only if Prana is persisting.

प्राणपरित्यागो हि सर्वत्यागः । तस्यानुपालनं - स्वस्थस्य स्वस्थावृत्तानुवृत्तिः
आतुरस्यविकारप्रशमनेऽग्रमादः ॥

(च.सू. ११/४)

By the end of life, there is an end to everything. That can be achieved by following the rules meant for healthy individuals and by non-negligence in the treatment of diseases if they occur. Here also, the importance is given for Swasthyapalana in achieving Prana (long life span as commented by Cakrapani on Ca. Su. 11/3). An individual is said to be Swastha or healthy only when Dosas, Dhatus, Malas, and Agni are functioning normally, and mind, soul, and sensory as well as motor organs are in tranquil (Su. Su. 15). Dhatusamyata can be secured by Cikitsa (Ca. Su. 16/34), and this Cikitsa is classified into Bhesaja and Abhesaja. Bhesaja type is subclassified into Rasayana and Vajikarana. (Ca. Ci. 1/1/4-6) under the category of Swasthasya Urjaskara. Both these have a greater role in Pranaisana as they fulfil both aspects of the achievement of Pranaisana.

Rasayana or Jara Cikitsa is one amongst the eight branches of Ayurveda, practiced extensively and

effectively for ages. Though chiefly concerned with improving the healthy status, Rasayana is also used as a curative treatment with effect. Thus, it serves the dual purpose of eradicating the ailments and keeping them away, thereby promoting and prolonging the lifespan.

DEFINITION

Rasayana Tantra is one that deals with delaying of ageing process, increasing intellect and strength, prolonging life, and curing disorders. Dalhana says that Vayahsthapana means prolonging life up to a hundred years, and Ayuskara means increasing the life span above a hundred years. According to others, Vayahsthapana means maintaining youth and delaying ageing. Cakrapani also has the same opinion.

Dalhana, while commenting on Su. Su. 1/6. opines that

रसानां रसरक्तादीनां अयनमाप्यायनं रसायनं, अथवा रसानां
रसवीर्यविपाकादीनां आयुःप्रभृतिकारणानामयनं विशिष्टं लाभोपायः रसायनं ।

The same was followed in his commentary on Su. Ci. 27/1-2 as the one which nourishes, Rasa, Rakta, etc. Dhatus, or the one which stabilises youthfulness and prolongs life with activities through its Rasa, Virya, etc., is called Rasayana.

CLASSIFICATION OF RASAYANA

(A) Two types have been mentioned in Ca. Ci. 1/1/16.

- Kutipravesika
- Vatatapika

This classification is based on the mode of

administration. Kutipravesika is one in which Rasayana is given with the person staying inside a closed Kuti, whereas Vatatapika is that in which Rasayana is administered with the patient exposed to Vata and Atapa. In other words, Kutipravesika is an indoor administration while Vatatapika is an outdoor administration of Rasayana.

Dronipravesika is similar to Kutipravesika with slight modification wherein the individual is made to stay in a Droni (made out of Palasa) for six months, consuming a milk diet (Ca. Ci. 1/4/7).

(B) Two types, as mentioned by Dalhana, based on their mode of action

- (1) Samsodhana - 'Dosasya Samsodhanadi Samsodhanam'
- (2) Samsamana - 'Samsamanam Nagabaladi Prayogadikam' Samsodhana and Samsamana, both are curative. Samsodhana type of Rasayana expels the aggravated Dosas, whereas Samsamana type pacifies the accumulated ones.

(C) Three types as per Dalhana's opinion.

- (1) Kamyā
- (2) Naimittika
- (3) Ajasrika

This classification is probably based on the utility of Rasayana.

Kamyā Rasayana is subdivided into Pranakamiya, Srikamiya, and Medhakamiya Rasayanas. i.e., to increase the life span, to prolong the life span, and to increase the cognitive abilities of the mind, respectively. "Naimittikam Vyadhinimittam," i.e., Naimittika type of Rasayana, is nothing but Rasayana specific to a disease. "Ajasrikam Ksiraghrtabhyasadikam," i.e., Ajasrika Rasayana, deals with the daily intake of milk, ghee, etc. Rasayana is to promote the body's immunity.

(D) Susruta has classified them into four types

- (1) Sarvopaghata Samaniya
- (2) Medhayuskamiya
- (3) Svabhavavyadhi Pratisedhaniya
- (4) Nivrta Santapiya

In this, Sarvopaghata Samaniya deals with Rasayana to counteract the disease process. Medhayuskamiya is one way by which an individual can increase their intellect and prolong their life. Svabhavavyadhi Pratisedhaniya delays the onset of Svabhavika Vyadhis like Ksut, Jara, Pipasa, Mrtyu, etc., and Nivrta Santapiya Rasayana rebuilds the physical and mental faculties following their disturbance due to the disease process.

It can be further classified into five types based on their benefits (Caraka Sutrasthana, 4th chapter).

- (1) Dirghayuskara - Jivaniya and Brmhaniya
- (2) Tarunyakara – Vayahsthapana

- (3) Balakara – Balya
- (4) Medhakara – Medhya
- (5) Rogahara - Roganut (specific to disease)

One more Rasayana variety has been mentioned in Ca. Ci. 1/4/36, i.e., Acara Rasayana or Nitya Rasayana, where an individual follows Sadvrta and Swasthavrta strictly and gets the beneficial effects.

Persons who are truthful and free from anger, alcohol and sexual indulgence; who do not indulge in violence and over exercise; who are peaceful and pleasing in speech, who practice Japa, Tapa, cleanliness, charity; who are stable and steady; who regularly offer prayers to Gods, cows, brahmanas, teachers, preceptors and aged people; who are compassionate and merciful; who go to sleep and awake at regular time; who habitually take ghee and milk; who are experts in the knowledge of rationality; who are free from ego; whose conduct is good; who are not narrow minded; who love spiritual knowledge; who have excellent sense organs, respect for elders; who believe in the existence of Gods; who have self control and who regularly study Dharmasastras will get best out of rejuvenation therapy. If persons endowed with these qualities practise rejuvenation therapy, they get all the rejuvenation effects described above.

UTILITY OF RASAYANA

दीर्घमायुः स्मृतिं मेधामारोग्यं तरुणं वयः ।

प्रभावर्णस्वरौदार्यं देहेन्द्रियबलं परम् ॥

वाक्सिद्धिं प्रणतिं कान्तिं लभते ना रसायनात् ।

लाभोपायो हि शस्तानां रसादीनां रसायनम् ॥

(च.चि. १/१/७-८)

An ideal Rasayana prolongs life, improves memory and intellect, promotes health, provides immunity against diseases, thereby helping an individual to lead an energetic life. It improves lustre and complexion of the body, tones the voice and speech, increases the acuity of all the sensory and motor organs, vitality, and vigour.

Rasayana keeps away Jara

Removes Daurbalya; cures diseases and overcomes even Mrtyu, and a person lives for a thousand years. The individual not only gets his life span prolonged but also attains salvation. In Astanga Samgraha and later classics, instead of Pranati, Vrsata was mentioned, i.e., Rasayana can also impart Vrsya properties (A.S. U. 49/3-4).

By Rasayana, the Syama (dark) complexion can be turned into Gaura (fair) complexion, and its withdrawal causes the other way. Rasayana words off old age, cures diseases, prolongs life span, gives strength to Caksuradi Indriyas, improves immunity against diseases, and acts also as Vrsya. With the help of Rasayana, Japa, Tapa, and Yoga, one can overcome even death. Rasayana, Tapa, etc., will cure, with their Prabhava, etc., the diseases which are considered incurable. The diseases

that show even the imminent signs of death can be superseded by the administration of Rasayana or by performing Japa, Tapa, etc.

Factors to be avoided during Rasayana (Ca. Ci. 1-2/3)

Aharaja

Substandard diet

Sour, salty, pungent, and alkali

Dry vegetables and meat with Sesame

Germinated cereals and pulses, freshly harvested

Contradictory, unwholesome, dry, Abhisyandi food

Softened, heavy, putrid, and stale food

Irregular food intake and food taken before the digestion of earlier food

Alcoholic drinks

Viharaja

Day sleep

Regular sexual intercourse

Irregular and excessive exercise

Over work

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Ayurveda describes its objectives in two broad ways: one is the preservation of health, and the second is the disease. For preservation of health, there is a detailed description of measures like Dincharya, Ratricharya, Rittucharva, Sadvritta, and periodic seasonal Panch-Karma. Details about lifestyle, diet, exercise, and personal and social hygiene have been described. Similarly, Rasayana-Chikitsa, a separate speciality branch of Ayurveda, is devoted mainly to preservation and promotion of health by revitalizing the metabolism and enhancing immunity. It has therapeutic potential in combating many dreadful diseases of the present times, like tuberculosis, diabetes, atherosclerosis, dyslipidemia, stroke, Alzheimer's, cancer, etc.

However, this holistic science cannot be entirely tested on parameters of today's science, which has having reductionist approach, but still there has been plenty of research work done on the Rasayana to apply them in the modern context. Different studies on Rasayana drugs have proven their efficacy in treating epilepsy, convulsive disorders, and psycho-somatic stress. Rasayana has also shown positive results in alleviating anxiety, apprehension, and keeping the mind calm and cool. Maximum studies on Rasayana have been done on their antioxidant & immune-modulation properties. Studies have concluded that Rasayana regulates the immunological and endocrine systems without damaging the auto-regulative functions of the organisms. Rasayana drugs have been reported to treat generalized weakness and afford protection from cyclophosphamide-induced leukopenia.

Possible protective mechanisms of Rasayana may be by immune-modulation, quenching free radicals, enhancing cellular detoxification mechanisms, repairing damaged

non-proliferating cells, inducing cell proliferation and self-renewal of damaged proliferating tissues, and replenishing them by eliminating damaged or mutated cells with fresh cells.

REFERENCE

1. Kashinath Shastri, Gorakha Natha Chaturvedi, Charaka Samhita with Elaborated Vidyotini Hindi Commentary, Sutrasthana, Chaukhambha Bharti Academy, Varanasi, 2005; 587.
2. Atrideva Gupta, Ashtanga Hridayam, Edited with Vidyotini Hindi Commentary, Sutrasthana, Chapter 1 verse 5, Chaukhambha Prakshan, Varanasi, 2016; 3.
3. Ajay Kumar Sharma, Kayachikitsa-IV, Chaukhambha Orientalia, Delhi, 2014; 310.
4. Acharya Y T, Shusruta Samhita, Edited with Nibandha Sangraha Teeka, Chikitsa Sthana, Chapter 27 verse 1, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan. Varanasi, 2009; 0498.
5. Eric L. Teasdale, Workplace stress. Psychiatry, July 2006; 5(7): 251-254.
6. <http://m.timesofindia.com/india/Indias-eating-habits-may-have-changed-but-not-nutrition-levels/articleshow/45655606.cms>.
7. <http://scroll.in/article/812278/> Every day, India sees 10 suicides related to drug abuse, and only one of them is from Punjab.
8. Ajay Kumar Sharma. Kavachikitsa-IV. Chaukhambha Orientalia. Delhi, 2014; 322.
9. Kashinath Shastri, Gorakha Natha Chaturvedi, Charaka Samhita with Elaborated Vidyotini Hindi Commentary, Chikitsasthana, Chapter 1-3 verse 30-31, Chaukhambha Bharti Academy, Varanasi, 1998; 39.
10. Kashinath Shastri, Gorakha Natha Chaturvedi, Charaka Samhita with Elaborated Vidyotini Hindi Commentary, Chikitsasthana, Chapter 1-4, verse 26, Chaukhambha Bharti Academy, Varanasi, 1998; 58.
11. Agnivesha, "Charak Samhita", with Charak Chandrika Hindi commentary, by Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi and Ganga SahayPandey, Chikitsa Sthana Chapter 1/1, Verse No. 5. Page.4. Chaukhamba Surbharti Prakashan, 2007.
12. Ambikadutta Shastri, Shusruta Samhita, Edited with Ayurveda Tattva Sandipika, Sutrasthana, Chapter 15, verse 3, Chaukhambha Sanskrita Sansthan, Varanasi, 2003; 56.